

A Synergetic Approach to Ensuring the Competence of Future English Learners

Kuvandikova Nilufar Oblokulovna¹

¹ O'zbekiston-Finlandiya pedagogika instituti

Abstract:

Learning a foreign language is a very important issue in the formation of the III-Renaissance proposed by the leader of our country. It is not for nothing that President Sh. M. Mirziyoev declared learning a foreign language as a priority issue for these reasons. From this point of view, it is important to use the basic concepts of synergetic in ensuring the creativity of future English language teachers. [5]. In this article, we have taken as a basis a synergistic approach to ensure the competence of future English language teachers. In the 70s of the 20th century, German scientist G. Haken and Belgian scientist, Nobel laureate I. Prigogine introduced a new methodology to science. G. Haken proved his views with clear evidence in his books "Synergetics" [1], and I. Prigozhin "Order from chaos"[2],("Poryadok iz khaosa").

Keywords: synergetiks, fluctuation, bifurcation, agglutination, paradigm, fusion.

Introduction. Today, in our country, to take the popularization of foreign language teaching to a new level and to organize systematic work for the development of the field, the formation and development of the professional competence of future foreign language learners in the education of the growing young generation is becoming the main demand of the day. Because the teacher's professional competence and the qualities reflected in it show that the shortcomings in the process of acquiring professional competence, being able to use the acquired competences in practice, and using this competence effectively teach students and attract students, means that the teacher has sufficient skills. The goal-oriented orientation of the teacher's professional training presupposes the formation of integral personal characteristics that act as direct indicators of the professional development of the teacher, which can be described with sufficient completeness with the help of the concept of "professional competence." Because one of the main requirements of the present day is the ability of the listener to have professional skills, to be creative and at the same time to be competitive, we can be sure that in the future it will deliver mature language specialists.

Methodology. Synergetic (from the Greek "senergeia" - "cooperation", - means "harmony") - the process of self-formation (organization) in complex systems in nature, at what stage of evolution chaos plays a positive role, the emergence of order from chaos, cases of deviation from regularity (fluctuation)), explores issues such as unstable and stable situations, linear and non-linear development, multiple alternatives of development. [3]

From the point of view of synergetic, every state of the social system is a state of bifurcation. This can also be applied to the phenomenon of a language with a social nature, that is, a certain type does not live forever in any language, but certain typological changes occur in each language as a result of historical development. An example of a situation of bifurcation in the language system is the point where the tendency of elements of one type to decrease and the other type to increase is observed in the language. For example, evidence shows that in Old English the fusion tendency prevailed, but in Modern English the agglutination tendency is increasing.

The emergence of various innovations in the typological signs of the Chinese, Mongolian and Arabic languages indicates that the development of these languages is in a state of bifurcation, and later it will pass to the stage of stable development - attraction.

Fluctuation is one of the main principles of synergetics, which means a departure from a steady state that can completely take over a system and completely change its order of existence. As an example of fluctuation in linguistics, we can cite the fact that synharmonism is almost disappearing in the material of the Uzbek language. Because synharmonism is considered a general phenomenon characteristic of Turkic languages, but this phenomenon is subject to fluctuations in the Uzbek language. Or, in Uzbek language, signs of a different type - the meeting of fusion processes is considered a deviation state-fluctuation in relation to the agglutination type. Many more such examples can be found in the language system.

Today, when thinking about economic synergetics and social synergetic, it is permissible to consider that the language system, which has a diverse nature, has its own "linguistic synergetic" (linguistic synergetic). In our opinion, linguistic synergetic [5] describes the general laws of self-formation in the language, the relationship between linguistic order and linguistic chaos, typological changes in the gradual development of the language, updates, processes of transition to another quality stage, bifurcation (the division of development into 2), polyfurcation (the branching of development into several directions), is a paradigm oriented to the interpretation based on the principles of attraction (stable state of self-attractive development, like magnetic poles), fluctuation (deviation from a stable state, deviation). It is called "language development based on the synergetic paradigm", and it is scientifically based that the language development takes place according to the laws of the synergetic paradigm. Based on the synergetic paradigm in linguistics, V. Arshinov, Ya. Svirsky, B. Gyortzel, I.A. German, G.G. Scientists such as Moskalchuk conducted special studies. The manifestation of the synergetic paradigm in the language system can be justified by the following.

Language, as an open system, develops through continuous interaction in a social environment. Language develops historically. In the process of language development, it is possible to lose existing features, acquire new features, and create new structures that are radically different from the previous state. For example, signs of Indo-European languages 2-3 thousand years ago, complex morphology characterized by fusion, such as strong synthesizing tendencies are giving way to new structures, agglutination and analytical tendencies. This situation fluctuated based on the synergetic paradigm of languages as dissipative structures. Gradually, fluctuation affected the system of agreements, affected the system of agreements, affected the system of agreements, as a result, the mechanism of bifurcation was activated, analytical forms took the place of inflectional devices, and agglutination began to take precedence over fusion.

It should be noted that the type of creole and pidgin languages (the process of creolization and pidginization) is formed under the influence of language contacts based on the synergetic paradigm. In this case, a new creole or pidgin language is formed according to the concept of dissipation (dissipate means "dispersion", one of the main principles of synergetic, which means the emergence of a new structure from one structure). In the process of creolization, the language acquires a new typological system, on the basis of fluctuation, bifurcation, dissipation, the language moves from one order to another, in which the corporate influence of two or more languages becomes important. But it should be emphasized that it is impossible to predict when the process of transition to a new level of quality will occur.

In the history of linguistics, there are different views on the evolutionary development and dynamics of language. Initially, in the 11th century, three development phases - amorphous - agglutinative - flexive stages are shown. By the 20th century, it was determined that the stadial development of languages takes place in the form of inflection - agglutination - amorphism. If this issue is approached from the point of view of the synergetic paradigm, some of its problematic aspects will be solved. Considering the development of linguistic types as a "linear" direction from simple to complex, in our opinion, is considered a one-sided approach. If we observe the changes in linguistic types, it becomes clear that they have a "non-linear" development trajectory. This condition can be compared to a curved sinusoid, gradually it develops according to the dynamics of a "curve". Fusion linguistic type is considered a priority for Turkish languages, especially Uzbek, but this instability is not insignificant for the language system. Because in the linguistic synergetic paradigm, such facultative processes, unstable situations are considered to be of great importance, they can be positively evaluated as creating a basis for the formation of new order and structures. In this regard, E.N. Knyazeva writes: "Instability leads to radical updates in open systems. In general, if there is no instability, then development is a burden. Restlessness means development, or in other words, progress is based on restlessness, random situations, fluctuations. In this sense, the linguistic types in the language are continuously changing from stable to unstable or vice versa.

The English language is at the point of bifurcation: fusion and agglutination is called a trend, in which the fusion language is tested and the places where agglutination is observed are analyzed on the example of the English language.[4] By analyzing agglutination in a fusion language and fusion in an agglutinative language, we aimed to prove from a practical point of view that languages have a polytypological character and that languages develop on the basis of a synergetic paradigm. In the later periods of language development, the process of strengthening of agglutinative-analytical signs is observed in English. This is also confirmed by factual data. In English, the agglutination type is active in the following places:

I. Agglutination in the process of water formation:

1. In noun-forming suffixes: -er, read+er=reader-ness, kind+ness=kindness; -hood; child+hood; -dom; king+dom=kingdom; -ceiling; friend+ship=friendship.
2. Adjectives in adjectives: -able; change+able=changable: al; form+al=formal; -ent: insist+ent=insistent: -ful: doubt+full=doubtful; -work: child+work; -less: hope+less=hopeless: -ous; dangerous+ous=dangerous.
3. Verbal suffixes: -ly: fluent+ly=fluently; -wise: clock+wise=clockwise; -ward: down+ward=downward; home+ward=homeward.
4. Verb-forming suffixes: en; deep+en=deepen; trace; symbol+ize=symbolize: modern+ize=modernize; ideal+ize=idealize.
5. Prefixes: anti-: anti+freeze=antifreeze; bi-: bi+lingual=bilingual; co-: co+author=c0-author; counter-: counter+attack=counter-attack; dis-: dis+satisfaction=dissatisfaction; en-: en+rich=enrich; hyper-: hyper+text=hypertext; inter-: inter+national=international; mis-:

mis+understand=misunderstand; non-: non+smoker=nonsmoker; over-:
over+estimate=overestimate ;poly-: poly+syllabic=polysyllabic; post-: post+war=postwar; pre-:
pre+school=preschool; re-: re+write=rewrite; sub-: sub+way=subway; ultra-:
ultra+violet=ultraviolet; un-: un+do=undo; under-: under+line=underline.

II. Agglutination in the forming process:

6. The plural form of nouns is formed by the agglutination method with the help of the suffix –s(-es), and only more nouns have the meaning of grammatical plural on the basis of fusion. In this case, the tendency of agglutination takes precedence over fusion: book+s=books; like day+s=days.
7. Genitive case: John's car_John's car.
8. Degree-forming additions in adjectives and adverbs formants -er and -est: strong+er=strongest, clean+est=cleanest.
9. Number generating formants: four+teen=fourteen, seven+ty=seventy.
10. In the verbs, the third person singular form of the present simple tense (Present Simple Tense) suffix –s (es): read+s=reads, discuss+es=discusses.
11. Continuous tense form of verbs: read+ing=reading, sing+ing=singing.
12. In English, the past tense form of regular verbs is agglutinated based on the tendency of agglutination. It should be noted separately that the main part of the verbs in the English lexicon is the main part of the correct verbs, and the incorrect verbs are more than 250. So, in English, the tendency of agglutination is more important than fusion in forming the past tense form of verbs. The Oxford Dictionary Thesaurus & Wordpower Guide, published in 2007, lists 271 irregular verbs. 140 of them are fused verbs in their pure state, 87 are incorrect verbs resulting from reduplication of fused verbs based on the method of prefixation (based on the addition of prefixes such as for-, mis-, out-, re-, un- to some of the 140 verbs), Some of the 44 are irregular verbs, some of which have been changed by the suppletive method, some of them have been combined on the basis of agglutination, and some have not been changed at all. So, in English, agglutination is more dominant than fusion tendency.

Summary.

1. Synergetics as a new paradigm of science explains the mysterious world, where laws such as dissipation, bifurcation, fluctuation, nonlinear development, coevolution explain the reasons for the existence and development of complex systems, in particular, the language system. In any language, the observation of other linguistic types along with the dominant linguistic type means "synergetics" in the language. After all, synergetics means the Greek synergeia - "cooperation", "harmony". It seems that every language develops on the basis of positive "cooperation" of several types.
2. As a result of the spread of various linguistic and non-linguistic influences in the language, new signs, morphological and syntactic structures appear. In particular, the presence of elements of fusion in Turkish languages, the meeting of agglutination and analytical tendencies in Indo-European languages, the development of the tendency of agglutination side by side with isolation in Chinese and Vietnamese languages, the formation of creole and pidgin languages as a result of the corporate influence of two or more languages are evidences that the language is a dissipative system. , shows that it develops on the basis of a synergistic paradigm for the calculation of various effects. It can be called a unique linguasynergetic paradigm.
3. The stadial development of linguistic types in the language has a "non-linear" development trajectory, that is, one linguistic type dominates for a certain time, in the course of historical

development, it develops according to the "curved line" dynamics based on the laws of fluctuation, bifurcation, and polyfuration of synergetics. In a certain period of time, the former dominant linguistic type is replaced by a facultative linguistic type, and later this type also gives way to another linguistic type. In this way, linguistic types have a development trajectory based on the main principles of the synergetic paradigm, such as stability-instability, priority-disorder, order-disorder.

4. From the point of view of the synergetic paradigm, the morphological structure and typological signs of languages are not criteria that indicate the level of people's thinking, worldview and rational development. In the history of religion, peoples who speak a language with a dominant linguistic type have created a high civilization and culture. An attempt to prove the "cultural decline" at a certain stage of history on the basis of typological characteristics of languages is considered a non-scientific (quasi-science, pseudo-science) approach to the issue.
5. Today, synergetics should fulfill the function of "metascience" (Greek meta- "after", "after all sciences"), its laws have gained universality, and all sciences consider it "theirs" and use them. American scientist T. Kun wrote in his work "Structure of scientific revolution" ("Scientific revolution structure") that the revolution in science is measured by the change of the approach to the phenomenon and the renewal of the paradigm. In this sense, synergetics can be accepted as a scientific paradigm of the 20th-21st centuries as a methodological basis for almost all scientific fields, as well as linguistics.

References.

1. Г. Хакен. Синергетика: Иерархии неустойчивостей в самоорганизующихся системах и устройствах: Пер. с англ.- М.: Мир, 1985. -423с.(Hierarchies of instabilities in self-organizing systems and devices)
2. Николис Г., Пригожин И. Познание сложного. Введение: Пер. с англ. – М.: Мир, 1990. - 344с.(Cognition of the complex)
3. Е.Н. Князева, С.П. Курдюмов. Основания синергетики. Синергетическое мироведение. – М.:КомКнига,2005.-240 с. (Foundations of synergetics. Synergetic worldview) Г. Хакен. Синергетика: Иерархии неустойчивостей в самоорганизуемых системах и устройствах: Пер. с англ.- М.: Мир, 1985. -423р.
4. A.U. Rakhimov. Researching the linguistic type of fusion based on a quantitative and synergistic approach (in the example of the Uzbek language)-Т.: 2009. 8 pages (Study of fusion language type on the basis of quantitative and synergetic approach (on the example of Uzbek language).
5. Sh. Safarov. Language theory and lingvomethodology.-Т.:2015 (Language theory and lingvomethodology)
6. Khakimova D.H. Professional competence of the foreign language teacher.<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/professional-compet>.